

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 132

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 132

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 132:0 A Song of Ascents.</p>	<p>Psa. 132:1 שִׁיר הַמַּעֲלוֹת זְכוֹר־יְהוָה</p>
<p>Psa. 132:1 Remember, O LORD, on David's behalf, All ^ahis affliction; ² How he swore to the LORD And vowed to "the Mighty One of Jacob, ³ "Surely I will not ¹enter ^amy house, Nor ²lie on my bed; ⁴ I will not ^agive sleep to my eyes Or slumber to my eyelids, ⁵ Until I find a ^aplace for the LORD, ¹A dwelling place for ^bthe Mighty One of Jacob."</p>	<p>לְדָוִד אֵת כָּל־עֲנֹתָיו : ² אֲשֶׁר נִשְׁבַּע לַיהוָה נָדָר לְאַבְרָם יַעֲקֹב : ³ אִם־אָבֹא בְּאֶהְל בֵּיתִי אִם־אֶעֱלֶה עַל־עַרְשׁ יְצוּעָי : ⁴ אִם־אֶתֵּן שְׁנַת לְעֵינָי לְעַפְעַפֵּי תְנוּמָה : ⁵ עַד־ אֲמַצֵּא מָקוֹם לַיהוָה מִשְׁכָּנֹת לְאַבְרָם יַעֲקֹב : ⁶ תִּנְהַ־שְׁמַעֲנוּהָ בְּאַפְרָתָה מִצְּאֲנוּיָהּ בְּשָׂדֵי־יַעֲר : ⁷ נִבְוָאָה לְמִשְׁכְּנֹתָיו נִשְׁתַּחֲוֶה לַהֲדָם רַגְלָיו : ⁸ קוֹמָה יְהוָה לְמִנוּחֶתָּךְ אֲתָה וְאַרְזֶן עֲנֹךְ : ⁹ כַּתְּנִיךְ יִלְבָּשׁוּ־ צִדְקָ וְחִסְדֵיךָ יִרְנְנוּ : ¹⁰ בְּעִבּוֹר דָּוִד עֲבָדְךָ אֶל־תָּשָׁב פָּנָי מִשִּׁיחָךְ : נִשְׁבַּע־יְהוָה אֶל־דָּוִד אֱמֶת לֹא־ יִשׁוּב מִמִּנְהָ מִכְּרִי בִטְנֶךָ אֲשִׁית לְכִסֵּא־לְךָ : ¹² אִם־יִשְׁמְרוּ בְנֵיךָ אֶל־ בְּרִיתִי וְעֲדוּתִי זֹו אֶלְמָדָם גַּם־ בְּנֵיהֶם עַד־יְעַד יִשְׁבוּ לְכִסֵּא־לְךָ : כִּי־בָתֵּר יְהוָה בְּצִיּוֹן אֲתָה לְמוֹשָׁב לָו : ¹⁴ זֹאת־מִנוּחֶתִי עַד־יְעַד פָּה־ אֲשָׁב כִּי אֲוֹתִיָּהּ : ¹⁵ צִיְדָה בְּרֶךְ אֲבָרְךָ אֲבִיוֹנִיָּה אֲשַׁבֵּעַ לָחֶם : ¹⁶ וְכַתְּנִיָּה אֶלְבִּישׁ יִשַׁע וְחִסְדֵיךָ רַנְּנוּ</p>
<p>Psa. 132:6 Behold, we heard of it in Ephrathah, We found it in the ^bfield of ¹Jaar. ⁷ Let us go into His ^{1a}dwelling place; Let us ^bworship at His ^cfootstool. ⁸ "Arise, O LORD, to Your ^bresting place, You and the ark of Your ^cstrength. ⁹ Let Your priests be ^aclothed with righteousness, And let Your ^bgodly ones sing for joy.</p>	<p>אֲתָה וְאַרְזֶן עֲנֹךְ : ⁹ כַּתְּנִיךְ יִלְבָּשׁוּ־ צִדְקָ וְחִסְדֵיךָ יִרְנְנוּ : ¹⁰ בְּעִבּוֹר דָּוִד עֲבָדְךָ אֶל־תָּשָׁב פָּנָי מִשִּׁיחָךְ : נִשְׁבַּע־יְהוָה אֶל־דָּוִד אֱמֶת לֹא־ יִשׁוּב מִמִּנְהָ מִכְּרִי בִטְנֶךָ אֲשִׁית לְכִסֵּא־לְךָ : ¹² אִם־יִשְׁמְרוּ בְנֵיךָ אֶל־ בְּרִיתִי וְעֲדוּתִי זֹו אֶלְמָדָם גַּם־ בְּנֵיהֶם עַד־יְעַד יִשְׁבוּ לְכִסֵּא־לְךָ : כִּי־בָתֵּר יְהוָה בְּצִיּוֹן אֲתָה לְמוֹשָׁב לָו : ¹⁴ זֹאת־מִנוּחֶתִי עַד־יְעַד פָּה־ אֲשָׁב כִּי אֲוֹתִיָּהּ : ¹⁵ צִיְדָה בְּרֶךְ אֲבָרְךָ אֲבִיוֹנִיָּה אֲשַׁבֵּעַ לָחֶם : ¹⁶ וְכַתְּנִיָּה אֶלְבִּישׁ יִשַׁע וְחִסְדֵיךָ רַנְּנוּ</p>
<p>Psa. 132:10 For the sake of David Your servant, Do not turn away the face of Your ^aanointed. ¹¹ The LORD has ^asworn to David</p>	<p>לְדָוִד אֵת כָּל־עֲנֹתָיו : ² אֲשֶׁר נִשְׁבַּע לַיהוָה נָדָר לְאַבְרָם יַעֲקֹב : ³ אִם־אָבֹא בְּאֶהְל בֵּיתִי אִם־אֶעֱלֶה עַל־עַרְשׁ יְצוּעָי : ⁴ אִם־אֶתֵּן שְׁנַת לְעֵינָי לְעַפְעַפֵּי תְנוּמָה : ⁵ עַד־ אֲמַצֵּא מָקוֹם לַיהוָה מִשְׁכָּנֹת לְאַבְרָם יַעֲקֹב : ⁶ תִּנְהַ־שְׁמַעֲנוּהָ בְּאַפְרָתָה מִצְּאֲנוּיָהּ בְּשָׂדֵי־יַעֲר : ⁷ נִבְוָאָה לְמִשְׁכְּנֹתָיו נִשְׁתַּחֲוֶה לַהֲדָם רַגְלָיו : ⁸ קוֹמָה יְהוָה לְמִנוּחֶתָּךְ אֲתָה וְאַרְזֶן עֲנֹךְ : ⁹ כַּתְּנִיךְ יִלְבָּשׁוּ־ צִדְקָ וְחִסְדֵיךָ יִרְנְנוּ : ¹⁰ בְּעִבּוֹר דָּוִד עֲבָדְךָ אֶל־תָּשָׁב פָּנָי מִשִּׁיחָךְ : נִשְׁבַּע־יְהוָה אֶל־דָּוִד אֱמֶת לֹא־ יִשׁוּב מִמִּנְהָ מִכְּרִי בִטְנֶךָ אֲשִׁית לְכִסֵּא־לְךָ : ¹² אִם־יִשְׁמְרוּ בְנֵיךָ אֶל־ בְּרִיתִי וְעֲדוּתִי זֹו אֶלְמָדָם גַּם־ בְּנֵיהֶם עַד־יְעַד יִשְׁבוּ לְכִסֵּא־לְךָ : כִּי־בָתֵּר יְהוָה בְּצִיּוֹן אֲתָה לְמוֹשָׁב לָו : ¹⁴ זֹאת־מִנוּחֶתִי עַד־יְעַד פָּה־ אֲשָׁב כִּי אֲוֹתִיָּהּ : ¹⁵ צִיְדָה בְּרֶךְ אֲבָרְךָ אֲבִיוֹנִיָּה אֲשַׁבֵּעַ לָחֶם : ¹⁶ וְכַתְּנִיָּה אֶלְבִּישׁ יִשַׁע וְחִסְדֵיךָ רַנְּנוּ</p>

A truth from which He will not turn back:

“^bOf the fruit of your body I will set upon your throne.

¹² “If your sons will keep My covenant

And My testimony which I will teach them,

Their sons also shall “sit upon your throne forever.”

Psa. 132:13 For the LORD has ^achosen Zion;

He has ^bdesired it for His habitation.

¹⁴ “This is My ^aresting place forever; Here I will ^bdwell, for I have desired it.

¹⁵ “I will abundantly ^abless her provision;

I will ^bsatisfy her needy with bread.

¹⁶ “Her ^apriests also I will clothe with salvation,

And her ^agodly ones will sing aloud for joy.

¹⁷ “There I will cause the ^ahorn of David to spring forth;

I have prepared a ^blamp for Mine anointed.

¹⁸ “His enemies I will ^aclothe with shame,

But upon himself his ^bcrown shall shine.”

יִרְנְנוּ : 17 שֵׁם אֲצִמִית בְּקֶרֶן לְדָוִד
עֲרֹכְתִי יָרֵךְ לְמִשְׁקֵי : 18 אוֹיְבָיו
: אֶלְבֵּישׁ בְּנֶשֶׁת וְעַלְיוֹ יִצְיֵץ נִזְרוֹ :

References

Psalm 132:1

^aGen 49:24; 2 Sam 16:12

Psalm 132:2

^aGen 49:24; Is 49:26; 60:16

Psalm 132:3

¹Lit *come into the tabernacle of*

²Lit *go up into the couch of*

^aJob 21:28

Psalm 132:4

^aProv 6:4

Psalm 132:5

¹Lit *Dwelling places*

^{a1} Kin 8:17; 1 Chr 22:7; Ps 26:8; Acts 7:46

^bPs 132:2

Psalm 132:6

¹Or *the wood*

^aGen 35:19; 1 Sam 17:12

^{b1} Sam 7:1

Psalm 132:7

¹Lit *dwelling places*

^aPs 43:3

^bPs 5:7; 99:5

^{c1} Chr 28:2

Psalm 132:8

^aNum 10:35; 2 Chr 6:41; Ps 68:1

^bPs 132:14

^cPs 78:61

Psalm 132:9

^aJob 29:14

^bPs 30:4; 132:16; 149:5

Psalm 132:10

^aPs 2:2; 132:17

Psalm 132:11

^aPs 89:3, 35

^b2 Sam 7:12-16; 1 Chr 17:11-14; 2 Chr 6:16; Ps 89:4; Acts 2:30

Psalm 132:12

^aLuke 1:32; Acts 2:30

Psalm 132:13

^aPs 48:1, 2; 78:68

^bPs 68:16

Psalm 132:14

^aPs 132:8

^bPs 68:16; Matt 23:21

Psalm 132:15

^aPs 147:14

^bPs 107:9

Psalm 132:16

^a2 Chr 6:41; Ps 132:9

Psalm 132:17

^aEzek 29:21; Luke 1:69

^b1 Kin 11:36; 15:4; 2 Kin 8:19; 2 Chr 21:7; Ps 18:28

Psalm 132:18

^aJob 8:22; Ps 35:26; 109:29

^bPs 21:3

Targum

Psa. 132:1 A song that was uttered on the ascents of the abyss. Remember, O LORD, for David, all his affliction. ² Who affirmed before the LORD a vow to the mighty one of Jacob. ³ I will not approach my wife, I will not ascend to the couch of my repose, ⁴ I will not give sleep to my eyes, slumber to my eyelids, ⁵ Until I find a place to build the sanctuary of the LORD, tents for the mighty one of Jacob. ⁶ Behold, we have heard it in Ephrat, we have found it in the field of the forests of Lebanon, the place where the fathers of old prayed. ⁷ Let us enter his tents, let us bow down to his footstool. ⁸ Arise, O LORD, abide in the dwelling-place of your rest, you and the ark in which is your Torah. ⁹ Your priests will wear clothing of righteousness, and your pious Levites will sing praise over your sacrifices. ¹⁰ Because of the merit of David your servant; when the ark comes through the middle of the gates, do not turn back the face of Solomon your anointed. ¹¹ The LORD has affirmed to David in truth, he will not turn from it: "One of the children of your belly I will set as a king on your throne." ¹² If your sons keep my covenant and this testimony of mine that I shall teach them, then your sons will forever sit on your throne. ¹³ For the LORD is pleased with Zion; he has desired it for his habitation. ¹⁴ This is the resting place of my presence forever; here I will dwell, for I have desired it. ¹⁵ Her provisions I will surely bless; and her needy shall have their fill of bread. ¹⁶ And her priests I will clothe in garments of redemption, and her pious will surely sing praise. ¹⁷ There I will cause to come forth a glorious king of the house of David; I have prepared a lamp for my anointed. ¹⁸ His enemies I will clothe with garments of shame; and his crown will glitter upon him.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

King David longed to build the Temple to the LORD, the Beis HaMikdash. Although the LORD did not permit David to build the Temple he was granted the privilege of gathering the construction materials. David composed this Psalm in reference to three separate events which were all related to the Temple. In his youth David struggled to identify the precise spot where the altar of the Temple was to stand. Towards the end of his reign, David built an altar on that spot. Finally, it a Solomon who constructed the Temple so that David's altar to the LORD was its focal point.

Notes on this Psalm

For David the construction of the Temple to the LORD was paramount. David had been raised from a shepherd boy to become Israel's greatest King. David wanted to honor and worship the LORD above everything. The Temple became a sacred place where the children of Jacob could offer themselves to the LORD and know of His presence. Today there is not one centralized Temple but rather many smaller places of worship where the presence of the LORD can be sensed. If you attend worship at one of these places how much do you honor that house of the LORD. For David honoring the LORD was paramount. David knew that everything that he was and had came from the LORD. The average person today does not think that way. The presence of the LORD through the Shekinah can be felt anywhere. The strongest place to feel the Shekinah is in a place of worship that is dedicated to the LORD. However, the congregation in said place of worship must want this to happen. To many places of worship are country clubs. If you belong to such a place do what you

can to change the attitude of the congregation to see their place of worship as a place to meet the LORD and not a social club.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

